

Inertial forces from relativistic and thermal effects of electromagnetic frequency sweeps

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Abstract

We investigate the thermal and relativistic effects produced when an electrically conductive object is moving in tandem with a source of a variable electromagnetic field. First, we derive an energy–frequency relation to quantify the temperature rise induced by such a field. This relation is then combined with the Lorentz–Fitzgerald contraction and time dilation from special relativity to identify a force, F_c , required to reconcile energy conservation between stationary and moving observers. We further relate F_c to the relativistic energy of a moving mass, extending the analysis to objects without electrical conductivity. This connection leads to the prediction of an inertial force F_{cf} generated by the frequency sweep of an electromagnetic wave (whether caused by relative motion or by internal modulation) that interacts with mass regardless of its electrical properties.

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1. Introduction

The study of relative motion between electrically charged bodies and sources of electromagnetic fields underpins many fundamental principles in both low and high energy physics [1]. The electrodynamics of moving bodies has been addressed through classical Galilean transformations as well as Minkowski spacetime formulations [2]. Pre-relativistic investigations predicted that charged bodies contract along the axis of motion [3]. Notably, Heaviside examined the electromagnetic effects of a moving charge under the assumption of an invariable surface charge distribution [3], while Searle [4] demonstrated that a charged sphere in motion contracts in the direction of travel, producing a field distribution similar to that of a charged ellipsoid.

Le Bellac and Levy Leblond [5] developed a Galilean-invariant formulation of electromagnetism by identifying two distinct non-relativistic limits for the electric and magnetic fields. Building on this framework, De Montigny and Rousseaux [6] applied a Riemann–Lorenz formulation to reinforce these results in the context of low energy phenomena and the electrodynamics of bodies moving at low velocities. Relativistic effects in electromagnetism have also been examined in [7], demonstrating that the magnetic component

of the Lorentz force emerges directly from the application of Lorentz contraction in the analysis of electrical currents. More recently, studies in time-varying media [8] have shown that, for any stationary observer, an accelerated electromagnetic wave exhibits relativistic effects with respect to laboratory time.

This study examines how a stationary observer measures the heat generated in an electrically conductive object that moves in tandem with a source of a variable electromagnetic field. The analysis incorporates the Lorentz–Fitzgerald contraction and time dilation to ensure that energy conservation is maintained between the thermal measurements of stationary and moving observers. We identify a force arising from the relative motion between the moving electromagnetic source and the stationary observer, a force that emerges as a direct consequence of Lorentz–Fitzgerald contraction, time dilation, and the requirement of energy conservation. The energy associated with this force is then compared to the relativistic energy of a moving mass, enabling an exploration of the physical consequences produced by the frequency sweep of an electromagnetic wave interacting with non-moving, non-electrically conductive objects.

Fig. 1 Cross-sectional area occupied by electric current. a) Spatial distribution of a steady (non-variable) electric current; b) spatial distribution of a variable electric current of frequency f .

2. Energy-Frequency characterization of Joule heating from variable electromagnetic fields

Joule power losses arise from the conduction of electric current through electrically conductive materials. These losses generate heat, raising the temperature of the conductor. The heat is subsequently transferred to surrounding bodies and media via conduction, convection, and radiation mechanisms [9]. The electrical resistance of an object is defined as

$$R = \rho \frac{Le}{S} \quad (1)$$

where R is the resistance of the object (Ω), ρ is the resistivity of the object (Ωm), Le is the length of the object (m), and S is the cross-sectional area (m^2) occupied by the flow of the electric current (see Fig. 1a).

The cross-sectional area S is determined by the skin penetration depth when the electric current is induced by electromagnetic fields. The skin depth is defined as

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\pi\mu f}} \quad (2)$$

where α is the skin depth of penetration (m), μ is the magnetic permeability (H/m), and f is the frequency of the source of the variable electromagnetic field (Hz) (see Fig. 1b).

In Fig. 1b, the induced electric currents are confined within approximately four skin depths [10]. By the nature of electromagnetic field penetration in conductors, beyond this depth the exponential attenuation of the field reduces current density (and therefore induced power) to negligible levels [10]. Therefore, the total Joule power losses produced by the induced electric currents are calculated as

$$P = \frac{\rho Le I^2}{4\ell} \sqrt{\frac{\pi\mu f}{\rho}} \quad (3)$$

where P refers to the Joule power losses (W), I represents the induced electric current (A) and ℓ is the characteristic length (m) of the electrically conductive object.

The heat losses from (3) can be used to estimate the temperature rise in electrically conductive objects. The transient temperature increase of such an object is given by (4).

Fig. 2 Schematic of a variable electromagnetic field source operating at energy E_1 and frequency f_1 , inducing current I_1 in an electrically conductive object.

$$P = \rho_m C_p Vol \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t} \quad (4)$$

where ρ_m is the mass density of the object (kg/m^3), C_p is the specific heat of the object ($\text{J}/(\text{kg} \cdot \text{K})$), Vol is the volume of the object (m^3), and ΔT is the temperature increment (K) produced after the time Δt (s).

Equations (3) and (4) are equivalent, each describing the same form of energy. Accordingly, the temperature rise in an electrically conductive object can be expressed as a function of the induced electric current I and the operating frequency f . That is:

$$\Delta T = \frac{\rho Le I^2}{4\ell} \sqrt{\frac{\pi\mu f}{\rho}} \frac{\Delta t}{\rho_m C_p Vol} \quad (5)$$

Suppose an electrically conductive object is positioned at the source of a variable electromagnetic field. As shown in Fig. 2, the source operates at frequency f_1 and induces an electric current I_1 in the object. After a time interval Δt_1 , the object's temperature increases by

$$\Delta T_1 = \frac{\rho Le I_1^2}{4\ell} \sqrt{\frac{\pi\mu f_1}{\rho}} \frac{\Delta t_1}{\rho_m C_p Vol} \quad (6)$$

After isolating the electrical terms I_1 and f_1 from the remaining factors on the right-hand side of (6), the temperature rise ΔT_1 simplifies to:

$$\Delta T_1 = C_1 I_1^2 \sqrt{f_1} \quad (7)$$

where C_1 is a constant defined as:

$$C_1 = \frac{\rho Le}{4\ell} \sqrt{\frac{\pi\mu}{\rho}} \frac{\Delta t_1}{\rho_m C_p Vol} \quad (8)$$

If the temperature rise ΔT_1 is known for a given combination of electric current I_1 and frequency f_1 , Eq. (7) can be applied to estimate the temperature rise ΔT_2 produced by a different induced current I_2 and frequency f_2 :

$$\frac{\Delta T_2}{\Delta T_1} = \frac{C_2 I_2^2 \sqrt{f_2}}{C_1 I_1^2 \sqrt{f_1}} \quad (9)$$

Since constants C_1 and C_2 both encapsulate the material properties, dimensions, and thermal time constant of the electrically conductive object, they are equivalent. Therefore, Eq. (9) reduces to

Fig. 3 Schematic of the measurement setup: a stationary observer at X records the temperature change of an electrically conductive object to determine ξ_1 , using a source of variable electromagnetic field with energy E_1 at frequency f_1 .

$$\frac{\Delta T_2}{\Delta T_1} = \frac{I_2^2 \sqrt{f_2}}{I_1^2 \sqrt{f_1}} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) provides a practical means of estimating the temperature rise in an electrically conductive object from the energy E of an electromagnetic inductive system:

$$E = \frac{I^2 L}{2} \quad (11)$$

where L is the equivalent inductance of the electromagnetic inductive system (H).

Equation (10) can also be expressed as

$$\frac{\Delta T_2}{\Delta T_1} = \frac{V_2^2 \sqrt{f_2}}{V_1^2 \sqrt{f_1}} \quad (12)$$

where V_1 and V_2 are the voltages induced by an electromagnetic capacitive system that delivers an electrical energy E given by

$$E = \frac{V^2 C}{2} \quad (13)$$

where V and C are the voltage (V) and capacitance (F), respectively, of the electromagnetic capacitive system.

Substituting the terms I and V from Eqs. (10) and (12) with their expressions in Eqs. (11) and (13) yields the following general form:

$$\frac{\Delta T_2}{\Delta T_1} = \frac{E_2 \sqrt{f_2}}{E_1 \sqrt{f_1}} \quad (14)$$

The energy–frequency relation in Eq. (14) is fundamental for describing the thermal energy generated in an electrically conductive object by a source of variable electromagnetic fields [11].

In the next section, Eq. (14) is applied to estimate the temperature rise in an electrically conductive object placed within a variable electromagnetic field, forming the basis for analysing how such measurements differ between stationary and moving observers.

3. Thermal discrepancy between moving and stationary observers

The parameters ΔT_1 , E_1 and f_1 characterize the electrothermal behaviour, material properties, and geometric dimensions of the electrically conductive object. These parameters are related as follows:

$$\xi_1 = E_1 \sqrt{f_1} \quad (15)$$

where ξ_1 is an electro-thermal performance constant defined as:

$$\xi_1 = \frac{\Delta T_1}{c_1} \quad (16)$$

Equation (15) directly quantifies the total electrical power converted into heat through Joule losses. It also possesses additive equality properties, derived from the principle of energy conservation and the linearity of electromagnetic waves [12]. These properties make it possible to estimate the temperature of electrically conductive objects when multiple sources of variable electromagnetic energy contribute to heat generation:

$$\xi_{final} \Delta t = \Delta t E_1 \sqrt{f_1} + \Delta t E_2 \sqrt{f_2} + \dots + \Delta t E_i \sqrt{f_i} \quad (17)$$

It should be noted that Eqs. (14) and (15) are valid only when the smallest dimension of the electrically conductive object is at least four times the skin penetration depth (Eq. 2) at the applied frequencies f_i .

Determining the values of the triplet ξ_i , E_i and f_i requires experimental measurements [10]. Alternatively, numerical methods such as the finite element method can be employed to obtain these values [13]–[15].

Suppose the observer at X in Fig. 3 conducts an experiment using an electromagnetic system to determine the constant ξ_1 for an electrically conductive object. The system consists of the object and a variable electromagnetic field source that delivers energy E_1 at frequency f_1 . After a time interval Δt_1 , the observer at X records that the object reaches a steady-state temperature of

$$T_1 = T_0 + \Delta T_1 \quad (18)$$

where T_0 corresponds to the initial temperature of the electrically conductive object.

For any other combination of energy E_2 and frequency f_2 produced by the electromagnetic system in Fig. 3, the observer at X finds that the resulting temperature rise ΔT_2 is given by

$$\Delta T_2 = \Delta T_1 \frac{E_2 \sqrt{f_2}}{E_1 \sqrt{f_1}} = \Delta T_1 \frac{\xi_2}{\xi_1} \quad (19)$$

Therefore, for any energy E_2 and frequency f_2 different from the reference values E_1 and f_1 , the observer at X records a temperature T_2 given by

$$T_2 = T_0 + \Delta T_2 \quad (20)$$

Now consider a second test in which the electromagnetic system from Fig. 3 is in motion relative to the observer at X (Fig. 4).

As the electromagnetic system begins moving toward the observer at X, the electromagnetic field's energy E_1 and frequency f_1 increase to E_2 and f_2 , respectively, due to the Doppler effect (Fig. 5). After a travel time Δt_1 , the observer at X estimates that the resulting temperature rise of the electrically conductive object should match the value calculated from Eq. (19), where ΔT_2 corresponds to the temperature that would be measured by the observer once the electromagnetic system stops moving.

Fig. 4 Stationary observer at X measuring energy E_1 at a frequency f_1 from a variable electromagnetic field source prior to motion.

From the perspective of the observer at X, the final temperature rise of the electrically conductive object should be greater than ΔT_1 and satisfy Eq. (21) once the electromagnetic system comes to rest.

$$\Delta T_2 > \Delta T_1 \quad (21)$$

Now consider a second observer moving in tandem with the electromagnetic system in Fig. 5.

From this observer's perspective, the Doppler effect is absent, and the energy E_1 and frequency f_1 remain unchanged (see Fig. 5).

Once the system comes to rest, the moving observer measures a temperature rise that coincides with

$$\Delta T_2 = \Delta T_1 \frac{E_1 \sqrt{f_1} \Delta t_1'}{E_1 \sqrt{f_1} \Delta t_1} = \Delta T_1 \frac{\Delta t_1'}{\Delta t_1} \quad (22)$$

where $\Delta t_1'$ is the travel time as measured by the moving observer.

Therefore, the final temperature of the electrically conductive object in Eq. (22) is lower than the value estimated from Eq. (19) by the observer at X (Fig. 5):

$$\Delta T_2 < \Delta T_1 \quad (23)$$

To satisfy the observations in Eq. (23), the observer at X must apply a compensation factor β to the estimates in Eq. (19):

$$\Delta T_2 = \Delta T_1 \frac{\beta E_2 \sqrt{f_2}}{E_1 \sqrt{f_1}} = \Delta T_1 \frac{\beta \xi_2}{\xi_1} \quad (24)$$

The compensation factor β must be a decreasing function of the electromagnetic field energy E_2 and frequency f_2 , as both increase due to the Doppler effect.

Relations (19) and (22) are equivalent only when the source of the variable electromagnetic field is stationary with respect to the observer at X, such that the Doppler effect is absent and the travel time Δt_1 equals $\Delta t_1'$.

Conversely, relative motion between the observer at X and the moving observer introduces a time delay between Δt_1 and $\Delta t_1'$ as a result of time dilation [16].

To determine the magnitude of the compensation factor β , the observer at X must account for the relativistic effects of length contraction and time dilation in the temperature estimation of Eq. (19). This can be demonstrated as follows.

Fig. 5 From the perspective of observer at X, the measured energy E and frequency f increase due to the Doppler effect.

From the perspective of the observer at X, there is a missing $\Delta \xi$ that accounts for the reduced temperature of the moving electrically conductive object compared with the temperature rise ΔT_2 in Eq. (19).

According to the observer at X, the sum of the electrothermal performance constant $\beta \xi_2$ in Eq. (24) and the missing electrothermal performance constant $\Delta \xi$ must preserve the principle of energy conservation relative to the original estimate in Eq. (19):

$$\Delta t_1 E_1 \sqrt{f_1} = (\Delta t_1 \beta E_2 \sqrt{f_2}) + (\Delta t_1 E_c \sqrt{f_1}) \quad (25)$$

where E_c denotes the missing energy, as determined from the observations of the observer at X.

Equation (25) can also be written in terms of the electrothermal performance constant ξ as follows:

$$\Delta t_1 \xi_1 = (\Delta t_1 \beta \xi_2) + (\Delta t_1 \Delta \xi) \quad (26)$$

Isolating the missing energy E_c from the remaining terms in Eq. (25) yields:

$$E_c = E_1 - \left(\beta E_2 \frac{\sqrt{f_2}}{\sqrt{f_1}} \right) \quad (27)$$

The magnitude of the compensation factor β in Eq. (27) is obtained by dividing Eqs. (22) and (24):

$$\beta = \frac{E_1 \sqrt{f_1} \Delta t_1'}{E_2 \sqrt{f_2} \Delta t_1} \quad (28)$$

The time delay between Δt_1 and $\Delta t_1'$ is obtained using the time dilation equation from the theory of relativity [16]. The formula is given by:

$$\Delta t_1' = \frac{\Delta t_1}{\gamma} \quad (29)$$

where γ is the Lorentz factor, defined as:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)}} \quad (30)$$

In Eq. (30), C denotes the speed of light (299,792,458 m/s), and v is the relative velocity (m/s) between the observer at X and the electromagnetic system (Fig. 5).

According to the relativistic Doppler effect, the Lorentz factor γ in Eq. (30) can be expressed in terms of the frequency sweep produced by the relative motion between the observer at X and the moving electromagnetic system [17]:

Fig. 6 Contraction of the electromagnetic field volume along the direction of motion as observed from X.

$$\gamma = \frac{f_2}{f_1} \quad (31)$$

Additionally, the relativistic Doppler effect introduces a difference between the magnitudes of E_1 and E_2 because the relationship between the electromagnetic field intensity and the cube of the frequency is a Lorentz-invariant quantity [18]:

$$K = \frac{I_N}{f^3} = \frac{CE_1}{vol_1 f_1^3} = \frac{CE_2}{vol_2 f_2^3} \quad (32)$$

where K is a constant, I_N is the intensity of the electromagnetic field (W/m^2), and vol is the volume of space (m^3) occupied by the distribution of the electromagnetic field.

Additionally, as noted by Searle [4] and Heaviside [3], the spatial distribution of a moving electromagnetic field undergoes contraction along the direction of motion:

$$\ell_0 = \frac{\ell'_0}{\gamma} \quad (33)$$

where ℓ_0 is the contracted dimension as measured by the observer at X, and ℓ'_0 is the corresponding dimension measured by the moving observer (Fig. 5).

In Fig. 6, the volume vol_1 of the electromagnetic field E_1 contracts along the direction of motion as the moving electromagnetic source approaches the observer at X. Consequently, the stationary observer measures an electromagnetic field volume vol_2 , given by:

$$vol_2 = \frac{vol_1}{\gamma} \quad (34)$$

Substituting Eqs. (28)–(34) into Eq. (27) yields the following expression for the missing energy E_c :

$$E_c = E_1 \left(\frac{f_2 - f_1}{f_2} \right) \quad (35)$$

From the perspective of the observer at X, the moving electromagnetic source in Fig. 5 has expended the energy E_c while traveling from point A to point B. Consequently, the observer concludes that a force must act within the spatial volume vol_2 such that

$$F_c = \frac{E_1}{\Delta\lambda} \left(\frac{f_2 - f_1}{f_2} \right) \quad (36)$$

where F_c is the force (N) and $\Delta\lambda$ is the distance (m) travelled by the electromagnetic system from point A to point B, as measured by the observer at X (Fig. 5).

Additionally, due to the nature of the electromagnetic field, the force in Eq. (36) can be expressed in multiples of Planck's energy:

$$F_c = \frac{Nh f_p}{\Delta\lambda} \left(\frac{f_2 - f_1}{f_2} \right) \quad (37)$$

Fig. 7 From the perspective of a stationary observer, a frequency sweep in an electromagnetic field may be indistinguishable whether produced by (a) a moving source of variable electromagnetic field or (b) a traveling electromagnetic wave of variable frequency.

where h and f_p are the Planck's constant (6.626×10^{-34} J·s) and Planck's frequency (2.952×10^{42} Hz), respectively, and N is the number of bits required to match the magnitude of the electromagnetic energy E_1 .

Equation (37) predicts that a moving source of a variable electromagnetic field generates a force in the reference frame of a stationary observer, such as the observer at X in Fig. 5. This force arises from the combined effects of length contraction and time dilation, which act to preserve the principle of energy conservation. Furthermore, *due to the traveling nature of electromagnetic waves, Eq. (37) implies that a stationary observer cannot distinguish between a frequency sweep produced by a moving source and a frequency sweep produced by a stationary source through internal modulation* (Fig. 7). From the stationary observer's perspective, there is no fundamental difference between a sweep caused by relative motion and one induced internally. Consequently, the mechanical effects described by Eq. (37) must arise independently of the sweep's origin, reinforcing the concept of a frame-invariant inertial force resulting from energy–frequency redistribution.

A similar phenomenon was described by Searle [4], who concluded that the spatial distribution of the electric field produced by a charged ellipsoid can be explained either with or without introducing relative motion between the charged body and a stationary observer.

Thus, for a traveling electromagnetic wave of variable frequency moving at the speed of light C , the force F_c can be expressed in terms of the frequency sweep as

$$F_c = \frac{Nh f_p}{C f_H} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \right) \quad (38)$$

where f_H is the highest frequency in the sweeping sequence.

The general expression in Eq. (38) indicates that the speed of a frequency sweep in an electromagnetic wave can produce a relativistic effect, perceived as a force by stationary electrically conductive objects.

Fig. 8 Initial conditions for Eqs. (41)-(42): object of rest mass m_0 located at point A prior to motion toward point B relative to a stationary observer.

The following section examines the physical implications of the interaction between the force F_c and the mass of stationary, non-electrically conductive objects.

4. F_c in relation to relativistic inertia and field-induced mass interactions

The force F_c parallels the relativistic forces observed when a mass moves relative to a stationary reference frame.

According to the theory of relativity, the mass of a moving object increases relative to a stationary observer, as given by:

$$m = m_0 \gamma \quad (39)$$

where m_0 is the rest mass (kg) of the moving object, and m is the relativistic mass as measured by a stationary observer.

Suppose an object of rest mass m_0 travels from point A to point B at velocity v relative to a stationary observer (Fig. 8). Before the object is set in motion, the stationary observer verifies that its rest energy is

$$E_0 = m_0 C^2 \quad (40)$$

where E_0 is the rest energy (J) [19].

Once the object moves, its total energy increases according to the relativistic mass relation in Eq. (39):

$$E = \gamma m_0 C^2 \quad (41)$$

where E is the total energy of the moving object (J).

Relative motion also produces a contraction of the object's spatial dimension along the direction of travel (Lorentz-Fitzgerald contraction).

From the stationary observer's perspective, this contraction can be associated with stored energy E_f , produced by a relativistic force F_f acting on the object's volume and surrounding space (Fig. 9).

As the object accelerates from A to B, the stored energy increases as

$$E_f = F_f \gamma r \quad (42)$$

where r is the travel distance (m) measured by the stationary observer.

By energy conservation, the sum of the stored energy E_f in Eq. (42) and the rest energy E_0 in Eq. (40) must equal the total energy E in Eq. (41):

$$E = E_f + E_0 \quad (43)$$

Fig. 9 Representation for Eqs. (42)-(45): stationary observer describes Lorentz-Fitzgerald contraction of a moving object as a stored energy E_f arising from a relativistic force F_f acting along the travel distance r .

Expressing Eq. (43) in terms of the m_0 gives

$$\gamma m_0 C^2 = F_f \gamma r + m_0 C^2 \quad (44)$$

which can be rearranged to define the relativistic force F_f in Fig. 9 as

$$F_f = m_0 a_f \quad (45)$$

where the associated acceleration (m/s^2) is

$$a_f = \frac{c^2}{r} \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma} \right) \quad (46)$$

Equation (45) is significant because, from the stationary frame, it is impossible to determine whether F_f originates from relative motion or from the influence of a gravitational field acting on the surrounding space. This indistinguishability echoes the equivalence principle of general relativity, which states that the effects of acceleration are locally indistinguishable from those of a gravitational field [16]. For example, using Earth's escape velocity (11,179.84 m/s) and radius (6,379,137 m) in Eq. (46), the stationary observer would predict a relativistic force F_f producing an acceleration of 9.798 m/s^2 (identical to the gravitational acceleration at Earth's surface) on the space surrounding the moving object.

This equivalence underpins the conceptual link between F_f and F_c , showing that both forces emerge from the same fundamental relativistic effects and must be proportional when viewed from the stationary frame.

Equation (46) can also be expressed using the Schwarzschild radius r_s of a hypothetical mass M interacting with m_0 :

$$a_f = \frac{r_s C^2}{2r^2}, \quad (47)$$

This allows the Lorentz-factor term in Eq. (46) to be written as

$$\left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma} \right) = \frac{r_s}{2r} \quad (48)$$

Substituting Eq. (48) into Eq. (45) yields:

$$F_f = m_0 \frac{r_s C^2}{2r^2} \quad (49)$$

Given this equivalence, it follows that the relativistic force F_f arising from mass motion and the force F_c generated by an electromagnetic frequency sweep share the same physical origin (relativistic length contraction and time dilation), both

acting to preserve the principle of energy conservation in the stationary reference frame.

From the stationary observer's perspective, these forces must therefore be proportional:

$$F_f = \alpha F_c = F_{cf} \quad (50)$$

Substituting the expression for F_c from Eq. (38) into the proportionality definition in Eq. 50 gives:

$$m_0 \frac{r_s c^2}{2r^2} = F_{cf} = \alpha \frac{N h f_p}{c f_H} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \right) \quad (51)$$

where α is proportional constant and F_{cf} denotes the resulting inertial force exerted by the frequency sweep of an electromagnetic wave on non-electrically conductive masses.

This proportional relationship states that F_f and F_c are manifestations of the same underlying relativistic principles, differing only in their physical context (mass motion versus electromagnetic frequency sweeps) yet both preserving energy conservation in the stationary frame.

This equivalence forms the foundation for Section 5, where bounds for the proportionality constant α are established and the broader physical implications of this inertial coupling are explored.

5. Bound on the proportionality constant α and implications for inertial coupling

As shown in Section 3, the frequency sweep of an electromagnetic wave produces a force F_c in electrically conductive objects due to Lorentz–Fitzgerald contraction and time dilation, ensuring the conservation of energy between frames.

Equation (51) extends this principle, showing that the same frequency sweep also induces an inertial force F_{cf} in objects of mass regardless of electrical conductivity. This inertial force is related to F_c by a proportionality constant α .

Determining realistic bounds for α is key to evaluating the possible magnitude of F_{cf} and its measurable effects.

5.1 Expressing α in terms of object mass

Rewriting Eq. (51) in terms of the rest mass m_0 of an object exposed to F_{cf} gives:

$$m_0 = \alpha \frac{N h f_p}{c f_H} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \right) \frac{2r^2}{r_s c^2}, \quad (52)$$

Here, r is the interaction radius (the effective spherical region where F_{cf} couples to the object's mass). This radius can be written in terms of Planck area A_P as:

$$4\pi r^2 = N A_P, \quad (53)$$

with $A_P = 2.6122803 \times 10^{-70} \text{ m}^2$.

In this framework, the number of bits N in Eq. (53) is taken equal to the N in Eq. (52), motivated by both the equipartition theorem [20] and the equivalence of forces from Eq. (50).

Substituting Eq. (53) into Eq. (52) yields:

$$m_0 = \alpha \frac{N^2 h f_p}{c^3 f_H} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \right) \frac{2A_P}{4\pi r_s} \quad (54)$$

5.2 Connection to Planck units

If Eq. (54) is recast in Planck units and expressed via the Schwarzschild radius r_s of m_0 , one obtains:

$$m_0 = N m_P \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (55)$$

where $m_P = 2.176434 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kg}$ is the Planck mass.

This relation indicates that any object's mass couples to F_{cf} in discrete multiples of $\sqrt{\alpha}$. The smallest interacting mass m_{min} is thus:

$$m_{min} = m_P \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (56)$$

5.3 Bounding α

Two physical considerations provide bounds for α :

1. Electromagnetic–Gravitational Force Ratio in Hydrogen

The simplest atomic system, hydrogen, gives a natural reference. Since F_c is electromagnetic in origin and F_f is mass–energy related, their ratio should be no greater than the ratio of gravitational to electric forces in hydrogen:

$$\frac{F_f}{F_c} = \frac{F_G}{F_E} = 4.39 \times 10^{-40} \quad (57)$$

where F_E and F_G refer to the magnitudes of the electric force and the gravitational force that take place in the hydrogen atom, respectively.

Substituting Eq. (57) into Eq. (50) gives:

$$\alpha = 4.39 \times 10^{-40} \quad (58)$$

2. Minimum mass equal to the electron mass

If m_{min} from Eq. (56) is set to the electron mass $m_e = 9.1093 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$, we find:

$$\alpha = 3.5 \times 10^{-45} \quad (59)$$

These two results set the plausible range:

$$3.5 \times 10^{-45} \leq \alpha \leq 4.39 \times 10^{-40} \quad (60)$$

5.4 Application to W and Z Bosons

The inertial coupling can be tested on massive, non-conductive particles such as the W and Z bosons. Using the de Broglie relation:

$$m_W c^2 = N_W h f_B, \quad (61)$$

$$m_Z c^2 = N_Z h f_B, \quad (62)$$

and the α -dependent mass relations from Eq. (55) [21]:

$$m_W = N_W \sqrt{\alpha} \frac{m_P}{\sqrt{2}} = 1.433 \times 10^{-25} \text{ kg} \quad (63)$$

$$m_Z = N_Z \sqrt{\alpha} \frac{m_P}{\sqrt{2}} = 1.625 \times 10^{-25} \text{ kg} \quad (64)$$

where f_B corresponds to the de Broglie wavelength (Hz), m_W and m_Z are the masses of the bosons W and Z, respectively, and N_W and N_Z refer to the number of bits required to represent the masses of bosons W and Z, respectively.

Substituting the bounds on α into Eqs. (63)–(64) and solving for f_B (de Broglie wavelength) gives:

$$1.23 \times 10^{20} \text{ Hz} \leq f_B \leq 4.37 \times 10^{22} \text{ Hz} \quad (65)$$

These frequencies lie within the gamma-ray spectrum (starting at $\sim 0.12 \text{ MeV}$ [22]), implying that a frequency sweep

in this band could, in principle, generate F_{cf} capable of coupling to the W and Z boson masses.

5.5 Final form of F_{cf}

The proportionality constant can also be expressed as:

$$\alpha = \frac{\kappa_B T_p}{E_v} \quad (66)$$

where $\kappa_B=1.380649 \times 10^{-23}$ J/°K is the Boltzmann's constant, $T_p=1.416784 \times 10^{32}$ °K is the Planck temperature, and E_v lies between 4.45×10^{48} J and 5.58×10^{53} J.

Substituting α into Eq. (51) yields:

$$F_{cf} = \frac{Nh}{c} \frac{f_p}{f_H} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \right) \frac{\kappa_B T_p}{E_v} \quad (67)$$

or, in terms of the electromagnetic field energy E_e as:

$$F_{cf} = \frac{E_e}{c f_H} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \right) \frac{\kappa_B T_p}{E_v} \quad (68)$$

5.6 Physical interpretation

Equations (67)–(68) show that the frequency sweep of an electromagnetic wave can generate a measurable inertial force acting on any mass, independent of electrical conductivity. This force arises fundamentally from relativistic length contraction and time dilation, ensuring the conservation of energy at the reference frame of stationary observers interacting with a variable frequency electromagnetic wave.

6. Potential detection methods and applications

The inertial force F_{cf} predicted in this work could be detected using ultra-sensitive interferometers, microbalances, or particle tracking systems in high-vacuum environments. A proposed test setup includes a neutral dielectric particle suspended in vacuum and exposed to a tunable, frequency-swept electromagnetic field. If the particle experiences displacement not attributable to radiation pressure or electrostatic effects, this would constitute direct evidence of F_{cf} .

Beyond detection, the nature of F_{cf} suggests novel applications. In space propulsion, internal frequency-swept fields could provide thrust enabling compact, long-duration propulsion systems. In nanotechnology or medicine, the force could be used to manipulate neutral particles or biomolecules with high precision and minimal heating. More broadly, confirmation of F_{cf} would open new avenues for probing relativistic field–mass coupling, and potentially contribute to emerging frameworks that connect inertia, information, and electromagnetic structure.

6.1 Example (revised as a constraint)

With $E_e=10^{-3}$ J and a sweep rate of 10^{11} Hz/s, a force sensor with threshold F_{min} constrains

$$\alpha \leq \frac{F_{min}}{E_e \cdot 10^{11} \text{ Hz/s}} \quad (69)$$

For $F_{min}=10^{-14}$ N (a magnitude within the sensitivity range of modern optical microbalances [23]), the experiment would set $\alpha \leq 10^{-22}$. This is many orders larger than the theoretical range (3.5×10^{-45} , 4.39×10^{-40}), so a null result would not yet challenge the theory; however, a positive signal at that level would instead imply a necessary reevaluation of α .

7. Conclusions

We conclude that the frequency sweep of an electromagnetic wave produces an inertial force F_{cf} that interacts with the mass of objects, independent of their electrical properties. This force arises from the combined effects of Lorentz–Fitzgerald contraction and time dilation, ensuring the preservation of energy conservation between electrical and thermal measurements obtained by both stationary and moving observers. The equivalence between F_{cf} and relativistic inertial forces suggests a fundamental link between electromagnetic frequency modulation and mass–energy interactions, with potential for experimental verification and technological application.

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